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UNPATH'D WATERS: The National Marine Inventories

Research Report: Work Package 6

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The National Marine Inventories

1.1 Introduction

The Unpath'd Waters Project aims to create better connections between maritime data and maritime collections from around and across the United Kingdom. At the heart of these collection are the National Monuments Records of England, the Isle of Man, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales (Figure 1). Each of these contain significant numbers of records that are maritime in nature and help to explain, interpret and enhance the understanding and enjoyment of maritime heritage. Although they record similar types of maritime data, often from similar sources, each is an individual National Record in its own right, with subtle and not so subtle differences in approach.

Figure 1: Extent of the different national records within the Unpath'd Waters Project

In the context of the Unpath'd Waters Project it is therefore useful to outline these National Records. This chapter aims to do this by providing a background to each National Record, a summary of the content of that record, the sources of information that have contributed to it, and the structure of the data contained within it. For each record, a final section then aims to 'look to the future' and highlight opportunities for improvement, challenges where they arise, and any key points learnt from involvement in the Unpath'd Waters Project.

The work was undertaken under the auspices of Work Package 6, although it supported and was supported by Work Packages 1 and 2.

1.2 Historic England's National Marine Heritage Record

Hefin Meara, Historic England

1.2.1 Background

The origin of Historic England's marine record dates to the early 1990's following the publication of the white paper 'This Common Inheritance', which tasked the Royal Commission on the Historical Monuments of England (RCHME) with the compilation of a database of historic wrecks and sites within territorial waters adjacent to England. The marine record, comprised of textual information stored in an Arches database and a corresponding GIS spatial depiction, has been maintained by a dedicated team of Marine Information Officers.

One of the key drivers for the redevelopment of HE's marine records has been the Heritage Information Access Simplified (HIAS) programme¹. Principle 2 of HIAS states that Historic England should be the first point of call for and primary trusted source of national datasets, such as the National Heritage List for England and national marine heritage dataset. While local authority HERs are the primary point of contact for terrestrial HER data, the remit for the marine zone sits firmly with Historic England. Historic England's marine records are publicly accessible online on the Heritage Gateway, under the heading "Historic England Research Records"².

1.2.2 Content of the Record

The marine component of Historic England's National Record of the Historic Environment (NRHE) comprises information on over 37,000 shipwrecks which have occurred within territorial waters adjacent to England. This figure can be broken down into approximately 6,000 wreck sites whose position on the seabed is known, and a further 31,000 wreck events which are known only from documentary sources.

These 'Casualty' records form a vital part of the record – they reveal the maritime archaeology potential of an area, and provide avenues of research to suggest the identity of newly discovered wrecks on the seabed.

¹ <https://historicengland.org.uk/research/support-and-collaboration/heritage-information-access-simplified/>

² https://www.heritagegateway.org.uk/Gateway/Resource_Desc.aspx?resourceID=19191

Given that we don't know the precise locations of these losses, they're assigned to an arbitrary set of coordinates, based around the named locations described within the sources.

When the record was originally developed it was decided that there would be a cut-off point at the end of the Second World War. However, as a result of funding from Medin, the scope of the record was expanded, and a project was undertaken to compile records for modern wrecks.

In addition to records for shipwrecks, the database also contains records of approximately 7,500 fishermen's fasteners, instances of fishing gear being snagged on a seabed obstruction. These are an indication of the potential for archaeological remains to be present on the seabed. There have been many examples of reports of the snagging of fishing gear, which on investigation were revealed to be nationally important shipwreck sites which were subsequently designated under the Protection of Wrecks Act 1973³.

The database also contains approximately 1,000 records for isolated findspots. These are reported via a variety of flowlines, including material reported as Droits to the Receiver of Wreck under the terms of the Merchant Shipping Act 1995, material discovered during the course of offshore development work such as the construction of offshore wind farms, or discovered during aggregate dredging operations.

The system also holds records for archaeological events such as geophysical surveys, diver investigations (Figure 2) and underwater excavations. In addition, the system holds a wealth of supporting information including bibliographic sources, as well as records for key people and organisations.

Information on buildings in the marine zone such as sea forts, piers and lighthouses, as well as historic aircraft crash sites make up the remainder of the record.

Figure 2: Diver exploring the designated wreck of HMS Colossus (© Cornwall & Isles of Scilly Maritime Archaeology Society).

³ See for example HMS Invincible - <https://historicengland.org.uk/listing/the-list/list-entry/1000052>

1.2.3 Sources of Information

The identified wrecks on the seabed are largely derived from a snapshot of the UKHO wreck index back in 1992, which has been further supplemented by other sources such as Diver guides, information supplied by divers, and sites discovered through the course of seabed development. This has been enhanced by the results of research and fieldwork funded by Historic England, including underwater archaeological survey, rapid coastal zone assessments, and aerial photograph interpretation.

Recorded losses were initially sourced from Richard and Bridget Larn's Shipwreck Index of the British Isles, which was then expanded upon from other sources including primary sources such as state papers, Board of Trade wreck enquiries, U-boat logs etc, as well as historic newspaper accounts. Previously this required visiting archives and searching through the original papers. It is now considerably easier thanks to the advent of online sources such as the British Newspaper Archive.

Information on fishermen's fasteners is derived from the various Kingfisher Books of Obstructions published by the Sea Fish Industry Authority. Findspots and isolated material are reported via the Receiver of Wreck, or through the various flowlines related to offshore development, such as the Marine Aggregate Industry Protocol for Reporting Finds of Archaeological Interest⁴.

1.2.4 Data Structure

One of the strengths of Historic England's shipwreck records is the quantity of information which is contained within structured fields and recorded using controlled vocabularies. In addition to craft type, the current record is structured to record details of the final voyage including – port of departure, port of destination, cargo, manner of loss, nationality and so on.

Historic England has been developing new data models for incorporation within the Mariner system during the Unpath'd Waters project. The new models build on the previous structure but allow for even more information to be captured in a controlled manner. One of the key principles is the move to recording the shipwreck site and the original floating vessel as different resources within the system. This allows for the capture of the full lifecycle of the vessel to be captured, including previous notable voyages and details of crew members.

New fields added to the record during this redevelopment includes – Builder, Place of Build, numbers of crew/passengers as well as numbers of crew/passengers lost. Fields in the recording structure use the FISH controlled vocabularies⁵ where appropriate.

1.2.5 Looking to the future

There are several key avenues of enhancement that will be of benefit to the English marine record:

- Inclusion of the Historic England's coastal and intertidal peat database which records detailed information on palaeolandscape features.

⁴ <https://www.wessexarch.co.uk/our-work/marine-aggregate-industry-protocol-reporting-finds-archaeological-interest>

⁵ <https://heritage-standards.org.uk/fish-vocabularies/>

- The enhancement of the event records, and a closer relationship with the OASIS flowline.
- Closer exchange of information with the UK Civil Hydrography Programme, to ensure that newly discovered features on the seabed are incorporated into the record quickly.
- Enhanced flowline of information with the commercial archaeology sector to improve the how information from development led work is captured within the record.
- Access to England’s marine historic environment records will be greatly improved with the launch of the public facing element of Mariner, the Arches based database currently under development.

1.3 Maritime Records in the Historic Environment Record of Northern Ireland

Rory McNeary, Department for Communities, Northern Ireland

1.3.1 Background

In 1992 the Department of Environment NI (DOENI) accepted responsibility for historic wrecks in Northern Ireland’s territorial waters under an Agency Agreement with the Department of National Heritage.⁶ It was recognised that fundamental to the successful management of the resource an understanding of the nature and extent of that resource would be required, and a number of initiatives were begun from 1993 including:

1. the recording of maritime-related sites on the coast and in the inter-tidal zone;
2. the compilation of documentary information pertaining to shipwrecks; and,
3. geophysical survey of inshore coastal waters.

These early initiatives formed the genesis of the wreck, and wider maritime records, that are held within the Historic Environment Record of Northern Ireland (HERoNI).⁷ In subsequent years NI Government archaeological curators have worked with the Centre for Maritime Archaeology (CMA) at Ulster University, and other relevant partners, to further augment these records.⁸

⁶ This initiative was in response to the Government white paper, *This Common Inheritance*; RCHME’s pilot, *Testing the Water* and the transfer of administrative function with regard to the Protection of Wrecks Act (PWA) 1973. See: Breen, C. 1996. Maritime Archaeology in Northern Ireland: an interim statement. In: *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 15(1):55-65.

⁷ See [Historic Environment Record of Northern Ireland \(HERoNI\) | Department for Communities \(communities-ni.gov.uk\)](https://www.communities-ni.gov.uk).

⁸ McNeary, R. and Westley, K. 2013. The Work of the Centre for Maritime Archaeology, University of Ulster: Past and Present. In: *Irish Maritime Heritage: Proceedings of the 3rd Galway International Heritage Conference 2013*: 11-24.

1.3.2 Content of the record

Maritime-related coastal and inter-tidal sites

The record of maritime-related coastal and inter-tidal sites has been generated through desk-top and field surveys initially undertaken from 1997 by a DOENI-funded Coastal Research Unit (CRU) and later by the CMA. These have been undertaken by region and sites assigned a unique number based on the relevant County and Irish Grid map sheet. To-date two major surveys have been completed: Strangford Lough, Co. Down⁹ and Rathlin Island, Co. Antrim¹⁰. These surveys have been published and the results integrated into the NI Sites and Monuments Record (SMR)¹¹. Further desktop surveys and fieldwork has been undertaken (principally the north coast) over the years. There are currently 938 Maritime Records recorded in the NI SMR.

Shipwreck Record

The origins of this record come from an initiative entitled MAP (Maritime Archaeology Project) which was adopted by DOENI in 1993. MAP was initially based at the Institute of Irish Studies in Queen's University, Belfast. The project's primary brief was to create a computerised database and paper archive of all maritime sites in NI's coastal waters; although the general view at the time was that the subject was largely confined to shipwrecks. Initial guidance was given by the Royal Commission on the Historical Monuments of England (RCHME) and the Joint Nautical Archaeology Policy Committee (JNAPC) data standard¹² adopted to record sites up to the 12 nautical mile limit, with a cut-off date of 1945.¹³ The sources of information used in compiling the register were largely documentary¹⁴, supplemented by the Wilson archive¹⁵, cartographic material, oral evidence and diver reports. Further in 1993 a Memorandum of Understanding between The Hydrographic Office and DOENI facilitated the transfer of information pertaining to known wrecks with good location evidence. The initial creation of this shipwreck record was completed in 1997 and a manuscript prepared for publication; however, the results were never published. The shipwreck archive was subsequently maintained and updated as a stand-alone database by the CMA as part of the Maritime Archaeology Services contract (1999-2015). The database currently contains 2,748 entries. The earliest wreck in the database dates to 1588 but the majority of entries are from the 19th and 20th centuries.

⁹ McErlean, T.R., McConley, R. and Forsythe, W. 2002. *Strangford Lough. An Archaeological survey of a maritime cultural landscape*. Belfast.

¹⁰ Forsythe, W. and McConkey, R. 2012. *Rathlin Island. An Archaeological survey of a maritime cultural landscape*. Belfast.

¹¹ See [Sites and Monuments Record | Department for Communities \(communities-ni.gov.uk\)](https://communities-ni.gov.uk/sites-and-monuments-record).

¹² Joint Nautical Archaeology Policy Committee (JNAPC), 1993. *Still at Sea, A Review of progress since the launch of the JNAPC's Heritage at Sea*. 8pp.

¹³ The 1945 cut-off has never been formally reviewed but the databases do include wrecks that post-date 1945.

¹⁴ The most frequently used sources were the nineteenth-century House of Commons Sessional Papers, the Parliamentary Papers containing the Board of Trade wreck returns and Admiralty wreck returns listing shipping casualties; Lloyd's List Index to Casualties 1741-1783 and Lloyd's List (containing information after 1783).

¹⁵ A pre-existing catalogue of c. 1000 wrecks compiled by Ian Wilson for his book *Shipwrecks of the Ulster Coast* (1989) and acquired by DOENI in 1993.

Figure 3: FPV Salar at Lacada Point, County Antrim, the site of designated shipwreck, La Girona, during a licensed dive inspection by the DAERA Marine Scientific Dive Team in September 2021 (©Crown Copyright).

The positional accuracy of these records is highly variable. In many cases the documentary sources provide limited information concerning the location of wrecks and only the broad general area is recorded. However, approximate positions have been assigned to all wrecks enabling the production of a general distribution map of wreck sites in Northern Ireland inshore waters. It was updated in 2009-10 primarily to improve positional information where possible. The database currently exists in three digital formats:

1. A Microsoft Word document with short descriptive records of each wrecking event;
2. As above but migrated to a Microsoft Access database; and,
3. ArcGIS shapefile with summary information.

Further in 2009-10 a 'known wrecks' database was compiled. This database contains records of known wreck remains on the seabed. It is based on information from multiple sources, but principally the UKHO shipwreck and obstruction database. Locations of wrecks have been checked against high resolution marine geophysical data (collected post-2008) where possible. Positional accuracy is variable but generally reasonable; the precise location of many of the entries is accurately recorded. The database contains fields reporting on the positional accuracy of each entry and the method used to obtain the position. The database initially contained 310 records, mainly 19th and 20th century wrecks, but now holds records of 382 shipwreck and downed aircraft locations. The database currently exists in one digital format: an ArcGIS shapefile with summary information.

1.3.3 Sub-littoral anomalies generated through geophysical survey

As part of the drive in the 1990s to quantify the maritime archaeological resource underwater geophysical prospection surveys (primarily side-scan sonar) funded (or part-funded) by DOENI were initiated. This initial geophysical research programme imaged c. 80 19th-20th century wrecks and c. 100 targets of further 'archaeological potential'.¹⁶ These data were integrated into the MR as contact sheets. A digital database was not created. Since 2008, geophysical analysis has centred on multibeam echosounder data. To date most research has been conducted on a dataset generated by the Joint Irish Bathymetric Survey (JIBs) which covered the seabed off the north coast between Fanad Head (Co. Donegal) and Fair Head (Co. Antrim) out to 3 nautical miles.¹⁷ These data have proved invaluable for updating positions of known wrecks and identifying anomalies. Similar work has been extended to the east coast where new multibeam datasets have become available (Torr Head to Belfast Lough (collected by the Royal Navy and supplied courtesy of the UKHO and Agri-Food & Biosciences Institute (AFBI)) and the INIS-Hydro program (a partnership between the UKHO, AFBI and Marine Institute) covers southeast Down and Carlingford Lough. These data have also been utilised in the investigation of submerged landscapes which has produced gazetteers of intertidal, submerged and buried sites in Northern Ireland with palaeo-landscape evidence, as well as sites with archaeological evidence.¹⁸

1.3.4 Looking to the future

The maritime heritage records held for Northern Ireland are largely borne out of initiatives undertaken in the 1990s and legacy issues persist with regard to data integration and structure. In *Conserving the Marine Heritage* (2019)¹⁹ DfC Historic Environment Division articulate a number of supporting objectives with regard to marine heritage record enhancement; these include:

- Enhance the Marine Historic Environment Record components of the Historic Environment Record of Northern Ireland and contribute to activities that might improve the investigation and analysis of these assets. Significant and/or at-risk heritage assets will be prioritised for recording.
- Maintain accessible and relevant records of the marine historic environment in the Historic Environment Record of Northern Ireland, the Historic Environment Map Viewer, the Marine Map Viewer and through other suitable means.
- Seek to raise public awareness of marine heritage assets, in partnership with the National Museums Northern Ireland (NMNI), Northern Ireland Museums Council (NIMC), the university sector and other relevant Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), through research, virtual access, archive collections and educational and outreach activities.

¹⁶ Quinn, R. 2007. The Assimilation of Marine Geophysical Data into the Maritime Sites and Monuments Record, Northern Ireland. In: *Historical Archaeology*, 41(3): 9-24.

¹⁷ Westley, K., Quinn, R., Forsythe, W., Plets, R., Bell, T., Benetti, S., McGrath, F., and Robinson, R., 2011, Mapping submerged landscapes using multibeam bathymetric data: a case study from the north coast of Ireland. In: *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology*, 40(1): 99-112.

¹⁸ Westley, K., and Henry, S. 2015. *Archaeological Assessment of the Seabed in Northern Ireland: Submerged Archaeological Landscape Potential*. Unpublished Report, 44pp.

¹⁹ See [Conserving the Marine Heritage: A Historic Environment Division Position Statement | Department for Communities \(communities-ni.gov.uk\)](https://www.communities-ni.gov.uk).

- Work with DAERA Marine and Fisheries Division, and other relevant partners, on matters of mutual interest with regard to survey and spatial data management planning.

Involvement with the Unpath'd Waters project has provided the opportunity for NI to engage with the other UK marine heritage agencies and collectively discuss and review the different methodologies and terminologies used within the separate UK marine and maritime records. As a result NI is currently undertaking a review of its marine heritage records and will be updating them in-line with the recommendations of the Unpath'd project. This will improve interpolation with other UK marine and maritime records and also ensure that NI's records are maintained in-line with current digital archiving standards. Once completed this will ensure that accurate data is available for the marine historic environment within NI waters and also provide the general public with a more accessible and user-friendly record.

1.4 Scotland's Marine and Maritime Record

Peter McKeague, Historic Environment Scotland

1.4.1 Background

Before 1995, only a handful of maritime losses had been recorded in the archaeological record. The Joint Nautical Archaeology Policy Committee's Code of Practice for Seabed Developers (1995), which aimed to encourage commercial operators to seek advice on the possible archaeological potential of proposed developments at the earliest opportunity, provided the catalyst for developing the maritime component of the National Record of the Historic Environment (NRHE).

The Marine (Scotland) Act and UK Marine and Coastal Access Act 2009 and reviews by Historic Scotland and BEFS (2009)²⁰ and Wessex Archaeology (2011)²¹ provided fresh impetus to develop the maritime record, through Project Adair^{22 23}, to support Scottish Ministers' policies for encouraging sustainable economic growth in the coasts and seas around Scotland. Again, emphasis on providing locational data for decision making was the priority.

A Core Trust Seal Certified repository, Historic Environment Scotland forms part of the Marine Environment Data Information Network (MEDIN) Historic Environment Data Archive Centre, along with the Archaeology

²⁰ Historic Environment Scotland and Built Environment Forum Scotland 2009 *Towards a Strategy for the Marine Historic Environment*

²¹ Wessex Archaeology 2011 *Scotland's Marine Data Heritage Audit*.

https://www.wessexarch.co.uk/sites/default/files/field_file/76680.01_Scottish_Marine_data_audit.pdf [accessed 15 August 2024]

²² RCAHMS and Historic Scotland 2012 *Project Adair Mapping Marine Heritage Sites to Support New Marine Legislation* <https://canmore.org.uk/collection/1539620> [accessed 14 August 2024]

²³ RCAHMS and Historic Scotland 2013 *Project Adair Mapping Marine Heritage Sites to Support New Marine Legislation Report for May 2012–March 2013* <https://canmore.org.uk/collection/1539633> [accessed 14 August 2014]

Data Service and the RCAHMW. MEDIN promotes best practice in managing and improved access to a broad range of marine industry datasets.

1.4.2 Content of the Record

The remit of the National Inventory is informed by, though not restricted to, the 12 nautical mile Territorial Sea defined in The Scotland Act 1998 and 200 nautical mile limit detailed in The Scottish Adjacent Waters Boundaries Order 1999.

With approximately 18,743 km of coastline along the high water line, 462,315 km² of sea and over 900 islands Scotland has a rich and diverse marine heritage if not the concentrations of wreck sites seen elsewhere across the UK.

The record comprises 4,639 wreck and aircraft locations where the position has been identified, and 23,233 documented, or reported, losses where the location has not been confirmed. There are 1,386 obstructions (unidentified material, fisherman's fasteners etc) as recorded by the UKHO – some of which may relate to wreck sites, and 5 reported findspots.

Information about maritime losses is managed seamlessly alongside records relating to intertidal sites (including 496 fish traps, nine kelp grids, and four intertidal crannogs.) and terrestrial buildings and sites (including 424 harbours and 145 lighthouses as well as many other maritime related monument types). To date there are no records for submerged landscapes or submerged peat deposits recorded in the national inventory.

1.4.3 Statutory Protection

In Scotland, the Protection of Wrecks Act 1973 was replaced with Part 5 of the Marine (Scotland) Act 2010, bringing marine heritage protection in Scotland into line with nature conservation, as part of a common approach to the protection of our natural and cultural marine heritage. To date there are eight Historic Marine Protected Areas, with three awaiting decision by Scottish Government. A small number of wreck locations, including those of the German High Seas Fleet in Scapa Flow are still protected through Scheduling. Sites on land and in the intertidal zone are protected through terrestrial designations, primarily Scheduled Monument and Listed Building legislation.

Administered by the Ministry of Defence, a number of wrecks are protected through the Protection of Military Remains Act 1986 either as Controlled Sites or Protected Places.

1.4.4 Accessing data

The maritime record is searchable online through PastMap and Canmore. [PastMap](#) is a map based browser providing location based searching across Designated Datasets (including Historic Marine Protected Areas, Scheduled Monuments and sites protected under The Protection of Military Remains Act 1986), [Canmore](#) records and many Historic Environment Records. Although the underlying data structure stores terrestrial, inter-tidal and maritime records in a single seamless database, for ease of use, terrestrial and maritime records are presented as separate layers. Users may either query individual records, linking through to more

detailed information on related web pages, or undertake area based searches across one or more datasets and download key information as either a .csv or .kml file under an Open Government Licence.

Figure 4: Data structure and workflow for the National Record of the Historic Environment (Scotland) illustrating the relationship between the activities (events), sites and wrecks, and associated archives

Canmore records may either be accessed through links in PastMap or through simple keyword or advanced, structured, searches or map searches on the Canmore website. Users may also search by thesaurus term or by archive Collection.

Canmore inventory records act as an online index to associated archival material with summary totals for the key archive types (Photographs, Prints and Drawings, Manuscripts and increasingly Digital Images and other digital files). From there the user may explore detailed indexes of catalogued material, view digital images and digitised video clips.

Under The INSPIRE (Scotland) Regulations 2009, HES also publishes View (Web Map Services) and Download (Web Feature Services) Services for its Designated Datasets and Canmore. Updated in real time, they can be accessed from the HES Download Portal, through spatialdata.gov.scot and data.gov.uk, for marine related datasets, on the MEDIN portal. These services are published under an Open Government Licence with Ordnance Survey Presumption to Publish were relevant. The [Historic Environment Scotland download portal](#) also provides user friendly access to these datasets.

Both Scottish Government's National Marine Planning Interactive and SEWeb consume these services within their own map portals where they can be viewed alongside datasets from other providers. Users may also embed these services directly into their own GIS applications to use alongside their own project data.

1.4.5 Sources of information

The maritime losses component of the NRHE was seeded by a download of the wrecks and obstructions dataset in 1995 and again in 2012, supplemented by information trawled from the Lloyd's Register Shipwreck Index and other sources by Larn and Larn (1998) and Ian G Whittaker (1998). In contrast to England Wales, there is relatively little active research into maritime losses.

Beyond ingesting these datasets, new data is added to the maritime record from projects commissioned or sponsored by Historic Environment Scotland (HES), from research and commercial archaeology projects, information reported via the Receiver of Wreck or from the offshore renewable industry.

Key HES projects include regular diving inspections of HMPAs and scheduled monuments, potentially nationally important wreck sites and thematic surveys. Large area remote sensing surveys help monitor the remains of the German High Seas Fleet over time.

Key research projects include the work of Drs Colin and Paula Martin and Wessex Archaeology's Project Samphire which reached out to local maritime communities – from Residents to recreational divers, fishermen, harbour masters and scallop divers – to record maritime cultural heritage sites along the length of west coast Scotland ([Wessex Archaeology](#)).

Summary accounts of fieldwork across Scotland is reported annually through Archaeology Scotland's *Discovery and Excavation in Scotland* journal. OASIS, an online system for reporting investigations into the historic environment and linking research outputs and archives, is the preferred mechanism for reporting fieldwork to the relevant local authority Historic Environment Record and Historic Environment Scotland. For marine records a workflow is in place to seed a metadata record in the MEDIN portal.

Research into the intertidal archaeology of Scotland's coasts has been well served by The SCAPE Trust established in 2001. Working with local communities, SCAPE has an active survey programme along Scotland's coast.

1.4.6 Data Structure

The structure of the maritime record was informed by that of the terrestrial record. Additional fields were added to manage coordinates in Latitude and Longitude alongside the OS National Grid System and a Maritime Craft thesaurus, modelled on FISH Maritime Craft Thesaurus, introduced in the early 2000s. An additional table manages information about the vessel including nationality, port of registration, dimensions, method of propulsion as well as details of the last voyage including cargo.

Introduction of an Events module in the 2000s provided the opportunity to uniquely record and index separate activities within the database instead of adding information sequentially to a lengthy site description. Information from sources added as Events have been indexed as documentary sources. The Events module uses a local copy of the FISH Event Type Thesaurus for indexing recording events. This vocabulary is augmented by additional Event types to index activities relating to the documentary history of vessels.

One of the strengths of the NRHE is the relationship between the inventory and associated HES archives, including digital material (digital images and videos, spatial content and documents). For select records (The

Duart Point Wreck / [The Swan](#) and [HMS Dartmouth](#)) users may also explore links through to the relevant catalogue entries for the physical objects in the National Museums Scotland. In a similar vein, Canmore can manage links across to specialist third party websites. For example a user researching HMS Bullen (Canmore ID: <https://canmore.org.uk/site/255347>) and explore related information on UBoat.net (<https://uboaat.net/allies/merchants/ship/3385.html>).

1.4.7 Looking to the future

Development of the maritime record in Scotland has been informed by approaches current in the 1990s driven by the need to provide locational information (managed against the Site or Wreck) for planning purposes leading to multiple entries for the same vessel. Yet, there is so much more potential to be realised from the maritime record. Key enhancements include:

- Developing and publication of the spatial component, including spatial extents where known, of the Events module to better reflect the temporal history of wreck locations.
- Improving confidence in the Events records relating to the UKHO where the method of discovery is known.
- Developing *ship's biographies* to more fully document the lifecycle of vessels from commissioning, construction and naming, through journeys to loss in addition to the rediscovery and recording of wreck sites.
- Address the need to identify environmental hazards of historic wrecks (Potentially Polluting Wrecks project).
- Improving information ingest and publication from large area surveys and targeted projects to ensure better decision making and stewardship of the historic environment by stakeholders from archaeologists to the offshore renewables industry.
- Ensure that the potential of unique and expensively gather data is preserved and archived in line with the Marine Environment Data Information Network (MEDIN).
- Adding intertidal peat deposits to Canmore.
- Work with researchers to develop approaches to documenting submerged landscapes within the record.

1.5 The Maritime Component of the National Monuments Record of

Wales

Julian Whitewright, Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales

1.5.1 Background

The maritime component of the National Monuments Record of Wales (NMRW) began to be assembled in the 1990s alongside similar initiatives in England and Scotland. This work was undertaken by the Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales (RCAHMW) as part of its Royal Warrant to create and maintain a National Monuments Record. These records were initially curated alongside terrestrial

records by RCAHMW staff, but since 2007 have been part of the work of a dedicated ‘maritime’ member within the RCAHMW’s survey and investigation team.

In Wales, the remit of the RCAHMW extends to the limit of the Welsh sea area, as defined by the Welsh National Marine Plan (WNMP). This means that the maritime component of the NMRW extends beyond the 12-mile limit of territorial waters to the median line between Wales and its neighbouring countries; Ireland, England, Northern Ireland and the Isle of Man.

1.5.2 Content of the record

The maritime component of the NMRW comprises all the archaeological sites and monuments located beyond or below the mean high-water mark, numbering c. 8,300 records. This dataset is available for download from the Welsh Government’s DataMapWales portal²⁴. Notable groups of records include 50 prehistoric submerged forests, 218 fishtraps, and 360 crashed aircraft. Further records relate to harbour infrastructure²⁵, including 49 historic harbours, 162 charted anchorages and 186 individual quays/jetties/wharfs.

Records classed as WRECK are the largest single maritime site-type within the NMRW, numbering c. 6,200. These can be broken down further based the form of evidence that we have for them. The biggest group are for c. 4,700 ‘documented losses’ of ships, where there is documentary evidence for the loss of a vessel but no archaeological remains. The locational accuracy of these varies enormously, from the very detailed to the extremely vague! More tangible are the 1,350 records termed a ‘known wreck’ where the main evidence is archaeological material on the seabed. A further 152 records relate to ‘findspots’ usually of isolated archaeological material such as an anchor, or in some cases a cannon.

The numbers just summarised for most of the different site types within the NMRW are relatively static; a previously unrecorded harbour infrastructure, or a newly identified fish trap might be added, but only in very small numbers. By contrast, the numbers of records for known wrecks within the NMRW has increased from 877 in 2021 to 1,350 in 2024. This is a combination of genuinely new wreck discoveries because of offshore and intertidal survey work (below), alongside revision and review of older records based on UKHO data but requiring an update due to new survey data.

1.5.3 Sources of information

The shipwreck component of the NMRW has its origins in the UKHO wrecks and obstructions dataset for records of ‘known wrecks’, information from the Receiver of Wreck for ‘findspots’ and the Shipwreck Index of the British Isles compiled by Richard and Bridget Larn for ‘documented loss’ records. The latter have been further augmented in the past decade by a growing wealth of online resources, chiefly those provided by the Lloyds Register Heritage and Education Centre (LRHEC)²⁶; Lloyds Register of Shipping, Casualty Returns, Survey reports and plans, etc. Other notable historical sources that are now consulted as standard include

²⁴ <https://datamap.gov.wales/>

²⁵ See Whitewright, J., 2024. The Historic Harbours of Wales. In Documenting Maritime Heritage at Risk. Digital Tools, Communities, and Institutions, E. Shotton & O. Prizeman (eds), pp. 42-52. Abingdon: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003385097>

²⁶ <https://hec.lrfoundation.org.uk/>

Welsh Newspapers²⁷ (freely available online for the period 1804-1919), and the journal of the RNLI²⁸ (available online from 1852 onwards), both of which can provide details on the location and circumstances of wrecking events.

Within the Welsh sea area, significant offshore wreck survey work has been undertaken by the School of Ocean Sciences at Bangor University²⁹. Subsequent analysis has allowed many shipwreck identities to be revised and updated³⁰, with the results now incorporated into the NMRW. Work by the RCAHMW between 2022 and 2024 has allowed a major revision and expansion to the 'known wreck' component of the NMRW based on the latest wrecks and obstructions dataset published by the UKHO derived from their ongoing survey work. This element of the NMRW can now be updated on an annual basis as new survey data becomes available, and c. 80% of the known wrecks within the NMRW are cross-referenced against a UKHO ID. It can be noted that a significant number, especially within the intertidal zone, exist as records within the NMRW, but are not listed by the UKHO. Further survey data, often including newly discovered wrecks, is ingested into the NMRW because of commercial marine development, for which the RCAHMW is a statutory consultee. Meanwhile, the c. 150 known shipwrecks located within Wales' intertidal zone are subject to a targeted programme of survey work by the RCAHMW (Figure 5) to provide a 3D digital baseline of their remains and to create records of new discoveries³¹.

Figure 5: A 29m-long wooden shipwreck (NPRN 240862) within the intertidal zone at Cefn Sidan Sands, Carmarthenshire, during a photogrammetry survey by the RCAHMW in October 2023 (Image 2024-03-18_2116, ©Crown Copyright: RCAHMW)

²⁷ <https://newspapers.library.wales/>

²⁸ <https://lifeboatmagazinearchive.rnli.org/>

²⁹ See <https://beta.imardis.org/about>

³⁰ McCartney, I., 2022. *Echoes from the Deep*. Leiden: Sidestone Press. <https://www.sidestone.com/books/echoes-from-the-deep>

³¹ <https://skfb.ly/owCEK> for RCAHMW intertidal and coastal survey work.

1.5.4 Data structure

The NMRW uses the commonly adopted FISH Thesaurus³² as its vocabulary to differentiate between site-types. More specific fields within each record are not currently available, but standard terms, for example from the FISH Maritime Craft thesaurus are used within the long-text description. The Unpath'd Waters project has demonstrated the ability to accurately extract such field specific information from text descriptions (see Supporting Research Report for Work Package 2), demonstrating the potential to upgrade NMRW records with new fields, e.g. ship-type, in the future. This has the potential to allow better accounting for aspects such as the overall numbers of certain ship-types, which in turn will allow indicators of archaeological significance, e.g. rarity, to be better appreciated. All of the fields, both maritime and terrestrial, within the NMRW are provided bilingually, in Welsh and English, and this requirement should be borne in mind when planning future work.

1.5.5 Looking to the future

Proactively seeking better linkages between data sources has been a central feature of the Unpath'd Waters Project, especially where such sources are increasingly available online. In particular, two areas of work have emerged which must be continued:

- Proactive, targeted work to link shipwreck records to their UKHO IDs, and to ensure that records continue to be updated as new survey work (either public or commercial) is made available.
- Creation of linkages to historical sources such as those held by the LRHEC or RNLI, allowing for a much richer and more compelling understanding of the stories of individual ships and people.

Alongside this, it is critical that the organisations responsible for maintaining the maritime national monuments records, retain the ability to undertake or commission survey work in a strategic manner to ensure that potential gaps in the record are filled. This is particularly true for archaeological sites, of all types, located within the intertidal zone, and which can fall between fully terrestrial or marine coverage. These are amongst the archaeological sites most at risk of impact from climate change, and proactive preservation by record as a means to mitigate this is of the utmost importance.

1.6 The Isle of Man Historic Environment Record

Jude Dicken, Collections Information Manager, Manx National Heritage

1.6.1 Background

Manx National Heritage, a Project Partner, has benefited directly from the work of Unpath'd Waters. The project catalysed the development of a new inventory of marine heritage for the Isle of Man and consequently Unpath'd Waters was able to include that national marine heritage data inventory within the Unpath'd Waters Portal³³. The partnership led to Manx National Heritage reaching out formally to

³² <https://www.heritagedata.org/blog/vocabularies-provided/>

³³ See supporting Research Report for Work Package 1: DOI 105281/zenodo.14793824

independent shipwreck research specialist Adrian Corkill, devising a programme for him to work with them to create the inventory.

The territorial waters of the Isle of Man extend to 12 nautical miles or a point equidistant from neighbouring coastlines where the distance between jurisdictions is less than 24 miles. The total territorial sea area is about 4,000 square km, which is about 87% of the total area of the jurisdiction of the Isle of Man. The Isle of Man is therefore more sea than land.

1.6.2 Content of the Record

As of December 2024, a total of 1,967 underwater site and 1,089 vessel resources were discoverable on the public website³⁴. Manx National Heritage has also drawn from its museum, library and archive collections to provide a rich context to the wreck site resources, including digitised artefacts, historic photographs, burial records, and crew lists. The inventory and public website attracted other content providers (such as the Isle of Man Sub Aqua Club) to upload recent images and 3D models for inclusion on more than several of the underwater site resources. In 2023, this data was shared and uploaded to the public portals of the Archaeology Data Service and ARIADNE³⁵, and work continues to upload further detail and more resources.

1.6.3 Data Structure

The inventory and public website (isleofmanher.im) are built using Arches, the CIIM, and MimsyXG. The resource models used (underwater site, vessel, archive and bibliography) consist of ‘cards’ of information which contain ‘nodes’ analogous to the units of information in MIDAS Heritage (UK Historic Environment Data Standard). The CIIM (Collections Information Integration Middleware) transforms the collections data and images managed in MimsyXG (the Manx National Heritage collections management system) and serves this as updateable content (daily) to the Arches endpoint, specifically ‘Linked Resources’ visible on the map pin to the underwater site.

³⁴ <https://isleofmanher.im/>

³⁵ <https://unpathd.ads.ac.uk/> and <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/search?q=&publisher=Manx%20National%20Heritage>